

Annotation protocol for the Corpus of spoken isiXhosa

Introduction

This document gives the background to the use of abbreviations and glossing conventions in the Corpus of spoken isiXhosa. The document forms the result of years of work on the preparation of the corpus (Bloom Ström et al. 2023). For a background on the material collected for the corpus, see Bloom Ström (2018). The choice of abbreviations is based on searches of grammar publications and lexica of isiXhosa, the knowledge of the second author as a mother tongue speaking linguist, as well as regular meetings and discussions. In a few cases, we have invited other researchers with specialized knowledge, whom we have consulted. See acknowledgements at the end of the paper. Since the decision on a certain linguistic category and abbreviation is our own, with inspiration from many sources, we do not generally cite published sources. Most examples in this document are extracts from the corpus. Examples that are in addition to the ones from the corpus, come from the second author's intuitions.

This document is work in progress. We welcome any comments you might have, please email: eva-marie.strom@gu.se

We include a table of contents, to facilitate navigation in the document.

Table of Contents

Abbreviations and symbols	5
Part of speech tags	8
Glossing conventions	9
1. General guidelines	9
1.1 Symbols	9
1.2 Agreement: dots and numbers	9
1.3 Underlying forms	9
1.4 Palatalisation	9
1.5 Lexical items	10
1.6 Sounds and ideophones	10
1.7 Reduplication	10
2. The noun	10
2.1 Nouns, noun class prefixes and augments	10

2.2	Diminutives	11
3.	Adnominals	11
3.1	Numerals	11
3.2	Adjectives.....	11
3.3	Nominal relatives	12
3.4	Associative	13
3.5	Demonstratives.....	14
3.5.1	Presentative demonstratives	14
3.6	Quantifiers.....	14
4.	Nominal formatives	14
4.1	Proper names	14
4.2	Additive	14
4.3	Comitative	15
4.4	The similarity prefix.....	15
4.5	Locatives	15
4.5.1	Locative prefix and suffix	15
4.5.2	Locative ku-.....	16
4.5.3	Locative kwa-.....	17
4.5.4	Locative and instrumental nga-	17
5.	Copulas	17
5.1	Locative copula	17
5.2	Associative copula.....	18
5.3	Identifying copula	18
5.4	The copula verb be/ba - ‘be’ vs COP:.....	19
6.	Pronouns	19
6.1	Personal pronouns	19
6.2	Identifying copula + pronoun.....	19
6.3	Independent pronouns	19
6.4	Possessive pronouns	19
6.5	Independent possessive pronouns	20
6.6	Question particle / wh-words	20
6.7	na as emphasis.....	21
7.	Verb phrase	21

7.1	Subject markers	21
7.2	Subjunctive and potential subject markers	21
7.3	Infinitives (and noun class 15)	22
7.4	Extensions	22
7.5	Relative verbs	23
7.5.1	Relative vowel, subject relatives	23
7.5.2	Non-subject relatives	24
7.5.3	Relative suffix	24
7.6	Conjoint/Disjoint	24
7.6.1	Conjoint/Disjoint with imbricated roots	24
7.7	TAM	25
7.7.1	Final vowel	25
7.7.2	Recent past imperfective	25
7.7.3	Remote past imperfective	26
7.7.4	Participial	26
7.7.5	Future	27
7.7.6	Itive and ventive	27
7.7.7	Persistive	27
7.7.8	Formative se-/sele- ‘already’	28
7.7.9	Possibility modal marker noku-	28
7.7.10	Potential modal marker nga-	28
7.7.11	Imperative	28
7.8	Auxiliary verbs	29
7.9	Negation	29
7.9.1	Negative morpheme -a	29
7.9.2	Negative ending -anga	30
7.9.3	Negative imperative	30
7.9.4	Ironic negative	30
7.10	Conjunctions	30
8.	Adverbials	31
8.1	Adverbs	31
8.2	Place adverbials	31
8.3	Adverbials with -nye	31

9.	Parts of speech	32
9.1	Derived nouns	32
10.	Transcription conventions	32
10.1	Elided vowels	32
10.2	Glide formation with inserted ‘w’ or (possibly?) ‘y’	33
10.3	Metaphorical translations	33
10.4	Code-switch.....	33
10.5	Overlap	34
10.6	Abbreviations in Xhosa.....	34
10.7	Vowel coalescence with particles	34

Abbreviations and symbols

1SG	1 st person singular
2SG	2 nd person singular
1PL	1 st person plural
2PL	2 nd person plural
1	noun class 1
1a	noun class 1a
3	noun class 3, etc.
AC	adjectival concord
ADD	additive
ALR	already
APPL	applicative
AS	associative
AUG	augment
CAUS	causative
CJ	conjoint
COM	comitative
COP	copulative
DEM	demonstrative
DIM	diminutive
DIST	distal
DJ	disjoint
EMPH	emphatic
FE	formulaic expression (accompanied with footnote on meaning)
FUT	future
FV	final vowel
HORT	hortative
IDEO	ideophone

IMP	imperative
IND	indicative
INF	infinitive
INTJ	interjection
INSTR	instrumental
IPFV	imperfective
IR	ironic negative
IT	itive
LOC	locative
MED	medial (demonstrative)
NEG	negative
NCP	noun class prefix
OM	object marker
ONOM	onomastic
PASS	passive
PERS	persistentive (- <i>sa</i>)
POSS	possessive
POSSIB	possibility (modal marker)
POT	potential
PRO	pronoun
PROX	proximal
PRSV	presentative
PRT	participial
PST	past
Q	question particle/marker
RV	relative vowel
REC	recent past
RECP	reciprocal
REF	referential

REFL	reflexive
REL	relative -yo
RV	relative vowel prefix
STAT	stative
SBJV	subjunctive
SM	subject marker
VEN	ventive
VOC	vocative

Part of speech tags

ADJ	Adjective
ADV	Adverb
CONJ	Conjunction
COP	Copula
DEM	Demonstrative
EMPH	Emphasis particle
FOR	Foreign
IDEO	Ideophone
INTER	Interrogative
INTJ	Interjection
N	Noun
NUM	Numeral
POSS	Possessive
PRO	Pronoun
PROPN	Proper noun
PROQUANT	Quantitative pronoun
V	Verb
VAUX	Auxiliary verb

SM.17-PASS\tie-PASS-SBJV 10-ox
'the oxen would have been harnessed' [BU160401D_a]

This convention is following Leipzig Glossing Rule 4D: If a grammatical property in the object-language is signalled by a morphophonological change (ablaut, mutation, tone alternation, etc.), the backslash is used to separate the category label and the rest of the gloss (Comrie et al. 2008, updated 2015).

1.5 **Lexical items**

Lexical items are translated based on context and does not always have to be the same. For example, *hamba* can be either 'walk' or 'go' depending on context. Some lexical items that occur in our data, especially from the far north of the Eastern Cape, are not recognised as Xhosa words in published works such as dictionaries. We then try to find that specific lexical entry in the dictionary of another relevant Nguni variety, e.g., Zulu. These words are not annotated in any special way in our corpus. Unknown lexical items are glossed with whatever discernible morpheme they might have, and the word as kept as is. For example, we have not been able to find the meaning of *-kuphahl-* in the token *e-kuphahl-eni*. In the glossing, this is therefore represented as LOC-kuphahl-LOC [BLN150924M].

1.6 **Sounds and ideophones**

Sounds and ideophones are glossed IDEO. For example, *zum* is used for the sound and idea of quickly getting into water, from *ukuzumka* 'sink in water'. Such ideophones are often preceded by (an inflected version of) *ukuthi* 'to say'. The ideophone *phofu* is sometimes added to express surprise, but also to mean 'actually'. The word *kanti* is added to expresses contrast and/or surprise. Primarily, we try to find English equivalents to put in the translation row, e.g., 'splash'. If there is no English equivalent, we put the Xhosa ideophone with a short translation in brackets.

3. *lozi*
lozi
flicker.IDEO
'Lozi (flickering of lights)' [PSJ150517O]

1.7 **Reduplication**

Reduplicated forms are rare. We add a gloss REDUP so that they can be found. A hyphen is used also in the transcription line, to match writing conventions in the language.

4. *phela-phela ngantsomi*
phela-phela nga-ntsomi
finish-finish.REDUP INSTR-9.story
'end of the story' [BU160401O]

2. **The noun**

2.1 **Nouns, noun class prefixes and augments**

Nouns are segmented into augment, noun class prefix and stem. The noun class number is indicated on the noun class prefix and the stem, but not on the augment.

5. *abantu*
 a-ba-ntu
 AUG-NCP.2-2.person
 ‘people’ [BU191231O]

The plural noun class is marked on the noun if it is in plural. It is sometimes tricky to separate the noun class 9 & 10 homorganic nasal NCP from the stem, therefore only the augment is segmented: *i-nkwenkwe* AUG-9.boy. In noun class 1a, there is just an augment followed by the stem *u-tata* AUG-1a.father. The same holds for 5 and 11, with polysyllabic nouns. The noun class prefix is present with monosyllabic nouns like *i-li-tye* AUG-NCP.5-5.stone.

2.2 Diminutives

The diminutives in Xhosa; *-ana*; *-anyana*; *-azana*, are all glossed as DIM. We segment the diminutive, especially when derived in a creative way. In some nouns, the form with the DIM is lexicalized. It is not always clear when something is lexicalized or not. We have left it to the segmenter/glosser to decide when to segment the suffix.

3. Adnominals

3.1 Numerals

All numbers such as years, ages, amount, etc. are written with letters, and not with digits. Longer numbers are written together in one cell e.g., *nineteenseventysix* in example (19), see also example (30). Numbers seem to fall into either noun class 1a or noun class 9. Sometimes, the noun class is identifiable by the preceding morphology, e.g., COP or AUG.

6. a *zayisix*
 za-yi-**six**
 SM.10-COP.9-9.six
 ‘They are six’ [BLN150924D_b]
- b *kweyesibini*
 ku-e-ya-i-si-**bini**
 LOC-RV-AS.9-AUG-NCP.7-7.two
 ‘on the second’ [MN180626O_a]

Numerals can also be predicated with *o-* instead of *a-* preceding the copula. We are not certain about the function of the *o-*, so we just gloss with the number for now, e.g:

7. *zoyithu*
 zo-yi-thu
 10-COP.9-9.two
 ‘They are two’ [NC191227D]

3.2 Adjectives

Adjectives are, like nouns, segmented into augment, prefix and stem. The prefix is glossed AC for adjectival concord. Only the AC is marked for number (8a), not the augment or the stem since the stems are not inherent to any noun class. The adjectival augment is different

from the nominal one, but they are not differentiated in glossing. The adjectival augment is in fact considered a merge between a prefix *a-* and the original augment, resulting in *e-*, *o-* and *a-*. In the predicative use, this prefix *a-* falls away in the noun classes with a nasal, such as (8b), with the result that *inkulu* has the same augment as the noun. In the case of noun class prefixes without a nasal, the augment is dropped altogether: *i-hashe li-khulu* [5-5.horse AC.5-big] ‘the horse is big’. This predicative adjective can be preceded by the subject marker: *li-li-khulu* [SM.5-AC.5-big] ‘it is big (e.g. the horse)’. In (8c), this means that the subject marker *i-* replaces (or merges with) the augment:

8. a *indlu enkulu*
 i-ndlu e-n-kulu
 AUG-house AUG-AC.9-big
 ‘The big house.’
- b *indlu inkulu*
 i-ndlu i-n-kulu
 AUG-house AUG-AC.9-big
 ‘The house is big.’
- c *inkulu*
 i-n-kulu
 SM.1-AC.9-big
 ‘It is big.’

This means that the glossing of (8a) and (8b) do not differ. The attributive versus the predicative uses can be read off the translation.

3.3 Nominal relatives

The nominal relatives have adjectival functions. The construction consists of a relative vowel (RV) and in some noun classes the adjectival prefix (AC); i.e. 2, 5, 7, 8, 10, 11, 14 & 15, see (9a). These are the noun class prefixes without a nasal that are often referred to as the ‘strong’ noun class prefixes. The other noun classes consist of just the RV + the lexical item. In those cases, the number follows the relative vowel (9b).

9. a *uluthi olubomvu*
 u-lu-thi o-lu-bomvu
 AUG-NCP.11-11.stick RV-AC.11-red
 ‘red stick’
- b *imoto ebomvu*
 i-moto e-bomvu
 AUG-9.car RV.9-red
 ‘red car’

The relative vowel is the same as the adjectival augment and can be considered to have an underlying prefix *a-*. In the predicative use, the relative vowel is dropped altogether, compare (10a) to (9a). In the ‘weak’ noun classes, the subject marker *i-* replaces (or merges with) the augment:

10. a *uluthi lubomvu*
 u-lu-thi lu-bomvu
 AUG-NCP.11-11.stick SM.11-red
 ‘the stick is red’

b *imoto ibomvu*
 i-moto i-bomvu
 AUG-9.car SM.9-red
 ‘the car is red’

The gloss RV gives the connection with relative verbs, which also qualify the nouns, see Section 7.5.

11. *Simtye elibhanqa esathambile umnandi kakhulu*
 si-m-ty-e e-li-bhanqa
 SM.1PL-OM.3-eat-SBJV RV.SM.5-COP.5-5.boiled.green.maize

e-sa-thamb-ile u-mnandi kakhulu
 RV.SM.5-PERS-soft-REC.DJ RV.3-nice a_lot

‘we eat it (maize) as boiled green maize, it is still soft, it is very nice.’
 [GX150515M_b]

When the relative vowel precedes an associative prefix, there is no subject marker. The agreement is the same as with the associative:

12. *baqul(a) owalapha*
 ba-qul-a o-wa-lapha
 SM.2-prepare-FV RV.1-AS.1-DEM.PROX.16
 ‘they prepared the one from here’ [BU160401D_e]

In the expressions like *bobabini* ‘both, the two of them’, we gloss the *o* as RV:

13. *omabini amakrwala*
 a-ma-krwala a-o-ma-bini
 AUG-NCP.6-6.initiate SM.6-RV-AC.6-two
 ‘both initiates’ [CA231210D_a]

3.4 Associative

The associative prefix is glossed AS with a number, e.g., AS.9. The vowel of the associative prefix is *a-* and it coalesces with the augment of the noun. We gloss with the underlying form:

14. *inqwelo yezigulane*
 i-nqwelo ya-i-zi-gulane
 AUG-9.wagon AS.9-AUG-NCP.8-patient
 ‘ambulance’ [BU151210S_b]

In the associative construction, there is an additional prefix *ka-* with the second noun if this is a noun of noun class 1a. In the case of the following example, there is no augment on the noun *gogo*.

15. *isimanga ke sikagogo*
 I-si-manga ke si-ka-gogo
 AUG-NCP.7-surprise then AS.7-AS.1a-1a.grandmother
 ‘Well the surprise of grandmother...’ [BLN150927M_a]

3.5 **Demonstratives**

Demonstratives are glossed e.g. DEM.PROX.7, with a three-way distinction: PROX, MED and DIST. The demonstrative have the part-of-speech tag DEM. The locatives, however, such as *apho* are part-of-speech tagged as ADV (adverbial) and glossed DEM.MED.16.

3.5.1 *Presentative demonstratives*

Forms like *nantsi* and *nanko* are presentative demonstratives. In glossing, they will be labelled as e.g., PRSV.DIST.9, with the demonstrative function implied. They use the same three-way distinction as regular demonstratives. The presentative demonstratives are not segmented in the corpus.

16. *Nanko enyuka*
 nanko e-nyuk-a
 PRSV.MED.1 SM.PRT.1-go.up-FV
 ‘There she goes up.’ [MN180626O_b]

3.6 **Quantifiers**

Quantifiers are only glossed for person or noun class number plus the lexical translation e.g.: *we-dwa* (2SG-alone) and *b-onke* (2-all). For an example of ‘other’ – which takes adjectival concord in isiXhosa – see (56).

4. *Nominal formatives*

4.1 **Proper names**

The morpheme *no-* is used in different naming strategies, we gloss it ONOM for onomastic:

17. *oo-nodatshaza*
 oo-no-ndatshaza
 AUG-ONOM-2a.wild.woman
 ‘Wild women’ (as a name) [MTF170609D_k]

4.2 **Additive**

The formative *kwa-* is a kind of focus quantifier, we gloss it as an additive (ADD). The vowel of the prefix does not coalesce with a following augment. Rather, the formative and noun are separated by a glottal stop:

18. *kwaʔumbona*
 kwa=u-m-bona

ADD-AUG-NCP3-maize
'also maize' (Oosthuysen 2016: 97)

The formative can also have the meaning 'still':

19. *Kwango-nineteenseventysix*
kwa-nga-u-nineteenseventysix
ADD-LOC-AUG-1a.nineteenseventysix
'still in 1966' [BLN150924D_b]

4.3 *Comitative*

The comitative *na-* is glossed COM, in its meaning as 'with', 'and'. The vowel *-a* merges with the augment. In the negative, the augment is still present, in contrast with the associative copulative, see Section 5.2.

20. *Kwakungekho nemali*
kwaku-nge-kho na-i-mali
SM.PST.IPFV.17-NEG-be.present COM-AUG-9.money
'There wasn't even money' [BLN150924D_b]

For noun classes 2 & 6, where the augment vowel is *-a*, the surface form does not show an augment, however, the underlying augment can be assumed based on the other noun classes.

4.4 *The similarity prefix*

The prefix *okwa-*, or *oku kwa-*, indicating likeness/resemblance (Mini et al. 2003: 930-931), is glossed with the meaning 'like', in lack of an abbreviation for such a similarity prefix. We assume that the augment prefix of the noun - *umthshakazi* in example (21) - has merged with the similarity prefix.

21. *Ugwece (hle) (o)komtshakazi*
u-gwec-e hle oko-u-m-tshakazi
SM.2SG-kneel-SBJV like like-AUG-NCP.1-bride
'You (should) kneel like a bride.' [BLN150924M]

When the form is *oku kwa-*, which is assumed to be the uncontracted form, we gloss *oku* separately as 'like', and *kwa-* AS.17.

4.5 *Locatives*

4.5.1 *Locative prefix and suffix*

The more general strategy to form locatives, from common nouns, is with the addition of the locative suffix that we segment as VCV; of the form *-ini* or *-eni*. They are glossed as LOC. The noun is also preceded by a prefix *e-*:

22. *embizeni*
e-mbiz-eni
LOC-pot-LOC

‘In the pot.’ [BLN150927M_a]

A final vowel of a noun stem glides preceding the locative suffix:

23. *esikolweni*
e-si-kolo-eni
LOC-NCP.7-school-LOC
‘In the school.’ [BLN150927M_a]

When the final vowel is *a* or *u*, there is no glide formation, or sometimes it’s optional. We include the full form of the noun.

24. *ekudleni*
e-kudla-eni
LOC-15.food-LOC
‘In the food.’ [BLN150927M_a]

In the case of palatalised stems, we do not include the underlying forms, see Section 1.4. Place names don’t use the suffix, but only the prefix *e-*:

25. *eGoli*
e-Goli
LOC-Johannesburg
‘In Johannesburg.’ [BLN150927M_a]

4.5.2 *Locative ku-*

The locative prefix is *ku-* when the noun is of class 1a and 2a. We also find this prefix with some nouns of classes 5 and 9. Due to vowel coalescence, the result can be either *kwi-*, *ku-*, or *koo-*. The forms are glossed LOC with the underlying form, showing the augment:

26. *Kwiliwa*
ku-i-li-wa
LOC-AUG-NCP.5-5.cliff
‘On the cliff.’ [BU160401O]

27. *koomama*
ku-oo-mama
LOC-AUG-2.mother
‘from the women’ [BU160401D_a]

Agreement markers *ku-* of noun class 17 are glossed as such, e.g., the associative AS.17. They are not to be mistaken for LOC. In these cases, the vowel also coalesces with the augment:

28. *phezu kweliwa*
phezu kwa-i-li-wa
above AS.17-AUG-NCP.5-5.cliff
‘on top of the cliff’ [BU160401O]

4.5.3 *Locative kwa-*

The form of the locative is *kwa-* when used with proper names.

29. *kwaNtu*
kwa-Ntu
LOC-Ntu
'in African culture' [GX150515M_b]

4.5.4 *Locative and instrumental nga-*

The morpheme *nga-* may express a range of different adverbial functions. In our glossing, we distinguish between instrumental INSTR and locative LOC. When it refers to location or time we gloss LOC (example 30), and with instrumental and other adverbial uses we gloss INSTR (example 31). The vowel *-a* of the prefix coalesces with the augment and we gloss with the underlying form (we assume an augment for classes 2 & 6):

30. *ngonyaka ka:twothousandandsix*
nga-u-nyaka ka-twothousandandsix
LOC.1-AUG-1a.year AS.1-1a.twothousandandsix
'When I was pregnant in 2006,' [BU160331M_F]

31. *ngeenkabi*
nga-ii-nkabi
INSTR-AUG-10.ox
'with oxen' [GX150515M_b]

Since we have examples in the corpus with the form *ngo-*, where the *o* cannot be explained by a merge with *u*, we analyse *ngo-* in such examples as an allomorph of *nga-*:

32. *ngokwesiHlubi*
ngo-kwa-i-si-Hlubi
INSTR-AS.17-AUG-NCP.7-Hlubi
'the Hlubi way' [STP160430D_a]

5. *Copulas*

5.1 *Locative copula*

The locative copula *se-*, used with the locative form of a noun and preceded by a subject prefix to mean that the person/thing is at this specific location, is glossed LOC.COP.

33. *isemoyeni*
i-se-moy-eni
SM.9-LOC.COP-3.AIR-LOC
'It is in the air' [GX150515M_a]

5.2 *Associative copula*

The associative copula, used in a range of functions relating to association and possession, is glossed AS.COP. The underlying form is *na-* but it coalesces with the augment of the noun. As with the comitative, an augment *a-* is assumed for classes 2 & 6.

34. *Linomntwan(a) oyintombazana*
 li-na-u-m-ntwana o-yi-ntombazana
 SM.5-AS.COP-AUG-NCP.1-1.child RV.SM.1-COP.9-9.girl
 ‘It had a child who was a girl.’ [PSJ150517O]

In the negative, the augment is dropped. This is the difference with the comitative (Section 4.3).

35. *u-m-bona ku-funek-(a) u-nga-bi-na-khul(a)*
 u-m-bona ku-funek-(a) u-nga-bi-na-khul(a)
 AUG-NCP.3-maize SM.17-require-FV SM3-NEG-be-AS.COP-11.weed
 ‘The maize must not have weeds (should not be with weeds).’ [GX150515M_b]

5.3 *Identifying copula*

The identifying copulative is glossed COP followed by noun class number. We do not assume the presence of an augment; the vowel belongs to the copula. The reason for this is that the copula in this form is also used with pronoun clitics of the form CV, without a preceding vowel, such as with *nga-bo* ‘it is they’ (and not *ng-abo*):

36. *oyinkwenkwe*
 o-yi-nkwenkwe
 RV.1-COP.9-9.boy
 ‘The one who is a boy’ [BU151210S_c]
37. *Ize kuz(e) abantu abangootata ngomso kuzothathwa*
 i-z-e ku-z-e a-ba-ntu
 SM.9-come-SBJV SM.17-come-SBJV AUG-NCP.2-2.person
- aba-nga-oo-tata ngomso ku-zo-thath-w-a
 RC.2-COP.2-2a-man tomorrow SM.17-IT-take-PASS-FV
- ‘And then tomorrow men go back to fetch..’ [BU160401D_a]

The negative copula is glossed NEG.COP followed by its noun class:

38. *Asingomama lo*
 Asingo-mama lo
 NEG.COP.1-1a.mother DEM.PROX.1
 ‘This is not mother.’ [MN180626O_b]

The negative copula is commonly heard as *ayingo-* rather than *asingo-*.

5.4 **The copula verb *be/ba* - ‘be’ vs COP:**

The copula verb *-be* should be glossed with the translation ‘be’ rather than COP. There might be a distinction between *-be* and *-ba*, but we do not make a distinction at this point.

39. *ubenetyala*
u-be-na-i-tyala
SM.2SG-be-AS.COP-AUG-5.case
‘You would have a case’ [BLN150924M]

6. **Pronouns**

6.1 **Personal pronouns**

Personal pronouns are glossed with PRO and number, e.g.: *mna* ‘I’ as PRO.1SG and *yena* ‘he/she’ as PRO.1 We also use PRO for the suffixed pronoun:

40. *Nomama walo*
Na-u-mama wa-lo
COM-AUG-1.a.mother AS.1-PRO.5
‘with its (vulture) mother’

6.2 **Identifying copula + pronoun**

The identifying copula with pronoun (*ndim*, *nguwe*, *sithi*, etc.) is segmented and glossed e.g. for the first person: *ndi-m* COP.1SG-PRO.1SG.

6.3 **Independent pronouns**

The vowel is segmented from the pronoun and glossed EMPH. The pronoun occurs with a number just like regular pronouns, e.g., *o-yena*/EMPH-PRO.1. We do not gloss with an underlying form of the vowel. Which is supposed to be *a* + a noun class specific vowel similar to the augment.

6.4 **Possessive pronouns**

Possessive pronouns have an agreement marker that we only gloss with the number, followed by POSS, plus the number of the noun class, e.g., 1-POSS.1, or the person such as in 9-POSS.1PL. We segment the possessive stems as *-m*; *-kho*; *-khe*; *-ithu*; *-inu*; *-bo*, etc. Note that *-ithu* and *-inu* are vowel-initial, which leads to coalescence such as with *bethu* in this example:

41. *abantwana bethu*
a-ba-ntwana ba-ithu
AUG-NCP.2-2.children 2-POSS.1PL
‘our children’ [BU160401D_a]

6.5 Independent possessive pronouns

Independent possessive pronouns are identical to the possessive pronouns, except that they occur with a preceding vowel *o-*, *u-* or *e-*, such as with the example *esam* ‘mine’ in (42). This vowel is simply glossed PRO and does not take any number:

42. *Uyasibona esam ngoku?*
 U-ya-si-bon-a e-sa-m ngoku
 SM.2SG-DJ-OM.7-see-FV PRO-7-POSS.1SG now
 ‘Do you see mine now?’ [GU151208D_f]

Noun class 17 agreement gives a locative interpretation, and can in turn be preceded by locative *ku-* to render the meaning ‘at theirs’ in (43):

43. *umntwana oyinkwenkwe obehleli ngasendlini kokwabo*
 u-m-ntwana o-yi-nkwenkwe obe-hleli
 AUG-NCP.1-1.child RV.SM.1-COP.9-9.boy RV.SM.IPFV.REC.1-sit

 nga-se-ndl-ini ku-o-kwa-bo
 LOC-LOC.COP.9.house-LOC LOC-PRO-17-POSS.PL.3

 ‘a boy child sitting by a house at his home’ [BU151210S_c]

44. *kukowabo*
 Ku-k-o-wa-bo
 SM.17-COP.17-PRO-3-POSS.3PL
 ‘It is their home.’ [GU151208D_f]

45. *kulomalume*
 Ku-la-u-malume
 LOC-AS.5-AUG-1a.uncle
 ‘it is at uncle’s’ [PSJ150517O_b]

6.6 Question particle / wh-words

Only the question particle *-na* is glossed Q. The other question particles like *-ni* and *-phi* have specific question word meanings that should be shown in the glossings, i.e., ‘what’ or ‘which’. However, *ntoni* from class 9 is an exception since it has become the default form for ‘what’. It is therefore not segmented and glossed ‘9.what’. Also *-njani* is not segmented and is translated ‘how’. The final vowel of the verb is not segmented when question particles are added: *W-enza-ni na?* SM2-do-what Q ‘What are you doing?’

Certain other question words like *kutheni* ‘why’ are not segmented and just glossed with their meaning.

6.7 *na as emphasis*

The particle *na* can be used for emphasis, i.e. not in a question. We analyse it as the question particle, but further research might show that it should be treated as a separate particle. We gloss this as EMPH, with the same POS-tag.

46. *Noba bangaphi na*
no-ba ba-ngaphi na
POSSIB-be 2-how.many EMPH
'No matter how many they are.' [GU151208D_f]

7. *Verb phrase*

7.1 *Subject markers*

For the present indicative, subject markers are just marked with number, e.g., SM.5. All other subject markers are marked with their respective TAM category, for example, past, participial, or hortative. SM comes first, then the TAM category, followed by the number of the noun class or person, e.g., SM.PST.2, SM.PRT.1SG, and SM.HORT.1. Some subject markers in different TAM categories may be identical to the present indicative (for example, both SM.1SG and SM.PRT.1SG are *ndi-*), but they are still to be glossed according to their function. Subjunctive and potential subject markers are exceptions, see below.

47. *Khawusibonise*
kha-u-si-bon-is-e
HORT-SM.HORT.2SG-OM.1PL-see-CAUS-SBJV
'Show us (mother)' [GX150515M_c]

Subject markers can have allomorphs, such as SM2.SG *u-* / *w-*.

7.2 *Subjunctive and potential subject markers*

The subjunctive and potential subject markers differ from the present indicative subject markers only in noun class 1, where it is *-a*. They are glossed SM.SBJV.1 and SM.POT.1:

48. *angaima*
a-nga-im-a
SM.POT.1-POT-stand-FV
'it can stand' [PSJ150517M_a]

All other persons and noun classes are glossed only with SM (without SBJV or POT). In the recent past subjunctive, the subjunctive function is marked in the subject marker as follows:

49. *ezi zinto zifuneka bezityile*
ezi zi-nto zi-funeka be-zi-ty-ile
DEM.PROX.10 NCP.10-10.things SM.10-need-FV SM.SBJV.2-OM.10-eat-REC.DJ
'The things that are necessary for them to eat' [GX150515M_a]

For the negative class 1 subject marker *ka-*, see 'negation' further down.

The by-phrase is with the instrumental *nga-* or with the identifying copula.

The stative can be either *-ek* or *-akal*, they are segmented as such and glossed STAT. Again, lexicalized verb forms such as *-funeka* ‘need, must’ are not segmented.

7.5 Relative verbs

7.5.1 Relative vowel, subject relatives

The initial vowel of relative verbs is glossed with the relative vowel RV. This is the same vowel as with nominal relatives (see Section 3.3) and is allomorphic (three-ways: *a-, e-, o-*). The relative vowel is followed by the subject marker, as seen in *abafundayo* ‘who are studying’ in (53).

53. *ingakumbi kubantwana abafundayo*
 ingakumbi ku-ba-ntwana **a-ba**-funda-yo
 especially LOC-NCP.2-2.child **RV-SM.2**-study- REL
 ‘Especially for children who are studying’ [BU160331M_e]

Vowel initial subject markers, on the other hand, are deleted. When the SM is deleted, it is still indicated together with the RV in the glossing, such as with *obhubhuzela* ‘that was blowing’ in (54):

54. *kwafika umoya obhubhuzela ngamandla*
 kwa-fik-a u-m-oya **o**-bhubhuz-el-a
 SM.PST.17-arrive-FV AUG-NCP.3-3.wind **RV.SM.3**-blow-APPL-FV

 nga-a-ma-ndla
 INSTR-AUG-NCP.6-6.force
 ‘there came a wind that was blowing with force’ [BU151210S_c]

Relative markers differ depending on if the verb follows an augmentless noun, such as *mzi* ‘homestead’ in the following example. This noun is augmentless because it is in turn preceded by a demonstrative. If *mzi* would have had an augment, the RV.SM.3 would be *o-*.² We gloss them the same way, so we are treating e.g., RV.SM.3 as allomorphic between *u-* and *o-*.

55. *Bathe xa bekusondela ngakulo mzi ulayitileyo*
 Ba-th-e xa be-ku-sondela
 SM.2-say-REC when SM.PRT.2-INF-approach

 nga-ku-lo m-zi **u**-layit-ile-yo
 INSTR-LOC-DEM.PROX.3 NCP.3-3.homestead **RV.SM.3**-light-REC.DJ-REL
 ‘It happened that when they came close to the house with the light..’ [PSJ150517O]

² Note that there is variation here. The second author would use an *o-* in this example (*olayitileyo*).

7.5.2 Non-subject relatives

We gloss non-subject relatives the same way as with subject relatives. If the subject marker is consonant initial (and therefore realised), we segment it from the relative vowel. The relative vowel is not numbered. If the relative vowel and the SM are merged, it is glossed RV.SM#. Non-subject relatives have an object marker, see the verb *esizidingayo* ‘that we need’ in (56). Note that the relative vowel in the subject relative *zibalulekileyo* ‘that are important’ in example (56) is dropped, since the verb form is preceded by a demonstrative and a pronoun.

56. *Ezinye iimfuno esizidingayo nezi zezona zibalulekileyo kwilali yethu*
 E-zi-nye ii-mfuna e-si-zi-dinga-yo
 AUG-AC.10-other AUG-10.need RV-SM.1PL-OM.10-need-REL
- na-ezi z-e-zona zi-balulek-ile-yo
 COM-DEM.PROX.10 COP.10-EMPH-PRO.10 SM.10-be.important-REC.DJ-REL
- ku-i-lali ya-ithu
 LOC-AUG-9.village 9-POSS.1PL
 ‘Other needs that we need and those that are very important in our village’
 [BU160331M_e]

Since subject relatives may also have an object marker, the only way to differentiate between subject and non-subject relatives is in the translation.

57. *kum nakulo ndimolekelelayo*
 ku-m na-ku-lo ndi-m-olek-el-ela-yo
 LOC-PRO.1SG COM-LOC-DEM.PROX.1 SM.1SG-OM.1-come.after-APPL-APPL-REL
 ‘..to me and the one that I am followed by.’ BU160401D_a

7.5.3 Relative suffix

When the relative suffix *-yo* follows the verb, we do not gloss the FV separately. So, we gloss *e-si-zi-dinga-yo* [RV-SM.1PL-OM.10-need-REL] in example (56), not *e-si-zi-ding-a-yo* [RV-SM.1PL-OM.10-need-FV-REL].

7.6 Conjoint/Disjoint

The present conjoint (short form) is not glossed as CJ, but is considered default, for convenience. Present disjoint forms are glossed DJ. In the recent past we gloss in full, and the suffix *-ile* is glossed REC.DJ, whereas *-e* is glossed REC.CJ. The present disjoint morpheme *ya-* can sometimes give a habitual reading, *u-ya-lamb-a* [BLN150924D_a] – but is still glossed as DJ – the habitual interpretation will be seen in the translation.

7.6.1 Conjoint/Disjoint with imbricated roots

Sometimes, the DJ form of the recent past can be very similar to the CJ form. There is sometimes only a tonal difference between the forms, but the same restrictions apply to the forms in terms of for example any following elements. They should be distinguishable, but since they are easily mistaken, we do expect there to be some CJ forms in the corpus, that in fact should be DJ.

62. *eGcinisizwe bendisenz(a) iprimary*
 e-Gcinisizwe **bendi**-s-enz-a i-primary
 LOC-9.Gcinisizwe SM.IPFV.REC.1SG-PRT-do-FV AUG-9.primary
 ‘At Gcinisizwe I was doing primary (school)’ [BLN150925M_b]

We treat this prefix as fusional in the corpus because when the subject marker is a vowel only, the form is further merged and hard to segment:

63. *ngo(kuya) ubundibuza phela*
 ngo(kuya) **ubu**-ndi-buz-a phela
 then SM.IPFV.REC.2SG-OM.1SG-ask-FV actually
 ‘..when you actually asked me [BLN150925D_c]

7.7.3 Remote past imperfective

This TAM has its origin in a complex construction (*ndabe ndibona > ndandibona*). It does not occur as non-contracted in the corpus. We gloss it as a fusional prefix, as with the verb forms *ndandikhula* and *sasithanda* in (64):

64. *Ngok(u)ya ndandikhula ndisemncinci sasithanda uyokutheza ehlathini*
 Ngokuya **ndandi**-khul-a ndi-se-m-ncinci
 then SM.PST.IPFV.1SG-grow-FV SM.1SG-PERS-NCP.1-young

sasi-thand-a u-yo-ku-theza e-hlath-ini
 SM.PST.IPFV.1PL-love-FV SM.1-IT-INF-gather.wood LOC-forest-LOC
 ‘When I was growing up, still young, we liked to go to gather wood in the forest..’
 [BU160331M_c]

7.7.4 Participial

The participial form is often similar to the indicative form. It is glossed SM.PRT. for subject marker plus participial.

65. *Khon(a) ukuze bathi xa belambile endleleni batye*
 khona ukuze ba-thi xa
 so that SM.2-say when

be-lamb-ile e-ndlel-eni ba-ty-e
 SM.PRT.2-be.hungry-REC.DJ LOC-9.road-LOC 2SM-eat-SBJV
 ‘so that, when they got hungry on their way, they could eat.’ [PSJ150517O]

The morpheme *s(i-)*: is used in participial forms before monosyllabic and vowel-initial stems. It is glossed as only PRT:

66. *babona izibane kude zisithi lozi*
 ba-bona i-zi-bane kude zi-**si**-thi lozi
 SM.PST.2-see AUG-NCP.10-10.light far SM.PRT.10-PRT-say flicker.IDEO

‘they saw lights glimmering far away’ [PSJ150517O]

7.7.5 Future

The future form *zaku* (and variations like *zau* etc.) is not segmented, neither are further contracted realisations like *yo-* and *zo-*. They are all just glossed with their surface forms as FUT:

67. *izakunilahlekisa*
i-**zaku**-ni-lahlekis-a
SM.9-FUT-OM.2PL-make_disappear-FV
‘it will make you disappear’ [PSJ150517O]

The same applies to *ndo* (SM.FUT.1SG). The full form would be either *ndi-zaku*, *ndi-zo* or *ndi-zoku*:

68. *Ndoya*
ndo-y-a
SM.FUT.1SG-go-FV
‘I will go.’ [BLN150925M_a]

7.7.6 Itive and ventive

Sometimes *yo-/ya-* and *za-* are used with itive and ventive meanings rather than future. In example (69), *y(o)-* is itive (going/movement away) and glossed IT, while *za(ku)* is ventive (coming/movement towards) and glossed VEN. They are glossed with their surface forms, no matter the realization (e.g., *za-*, *zaku-*, *zo-* etc.). When the auxiliary ‘go’ is used with an itive meaning, we gloss go.IT (cf. Auxiliary verbs).

69. *Kuye kwafika abantu bazakumthatha*
Ku-y-e kwa-fik-a a-ba-ntu ba-**zaku**-m-thath-a
SM.17-go.IT-REC.CJ SM.PST.17-arrive-FV AUG-NCP.2-2.person SM.2-VEN-OM.1-take-FV
‘There arrived people to take him (away)’ [BU151210S_a]

In cases where the subject marker and the itive are merged, the morpheme is analysed as fusional. This is the case with *wo-* in example (70), which is a merge of the past subject marker *wa-* plus the itive (*y*)*o-*. The same recording also has *wayofuna ukutya* with the same meaning:

70. *wofuna ukutya*
wo-fun-a u-ku-tya
SM.PST.1.IT-search.for-FV AUG-NCP.15-15.food
‘She went to search for food.’ [MN180626O_a]

7.7.7 Persistentive

The formatives *-sa* and *ka* are glossed PERS for persistentive. When occurring with negation, *ka* means ‘not yet’, and *sa* means ‘no longer’. They are glossed PERS regardless of polarity.

71. *ndangabisaphindela emsebenzini*
 nda-nga-bi-**sa**-phind-el-a e-m-sebenz-ini
 SM.PST.1SG-NEG-be-PERS-return-APPL-FV LOC-NCP.3-3.work-LOC
 ‘and never returned to work.’ [BLN150924D_b]

7.7.8 Formative *se-/sele*- ‘already’

The formatives *se* or *sele* are glossed ALR.

72. *Xa sefile ke ngo(ku) lo umSotho*
 xa **se**-f-ile ke ngoku lo umSotho
 when ALR-die-REC.DJ then now DEM.PROX.3 AUG-NCP.1-1.Sotho
 ‘Then when this Sotho is dead then.’ [BLN150924D_b]

7.7.9 Possibility modal marker *noku-*

This marker is glossed POSSIB:

73. *nokutya kunok(u)yenza loo*
 na-u-ku-tya ku-**noku**-y-enz-a loo nto
 COM-AUG-NCP.15-15.food SM.15-POSSIB-OM.9-do-FV DEM.MED.9 9.thing
 ‘...food could also cause that thing’ [GX150515M_a]

The marker also occurs as *no-*, see example (74).

7.7.10 Potential modal marker *nga-*

The verbal prefix *nga-* used as a potential marker is glossed POT:

74. *singavuya kakhulu xa sinofumana iblorho*
 si-**nga**-vuy-a kakhulu xa si-no-fumana i-blorho
 SM.1PL-POT-be.happy-FV a.lot if SM.1-POSSIB-receive AUG-9.bridge
 ‘So, we would be very happy if we could receive a bridge’. [BU160331M_e]

7.7.11 Imperative

The imperative is normally glossed with its translation plus the abbreviation IMP.

75. Hayi **qhuba** ndifun(a) ukuva nje ngokufunda kwakho
 hayi **qhuba** ndi-fun-a uku-va nje
 no continue.IMP SM.1SG-want-FV INF-hear just

 nga-u-ku-funda kwa-kho
 INSTR-AUG-NCP.15-15.study 15-POSS.2SG
 ‘No, continue, I just want to hear about your studying.’ [BLN150925M_b]

The plural suffix *-ni* is glossed as 2PL.

76. *Wathi unyana kaNtabatha buzani kulo*
 wa-thi u-nyana ka-Ntabatha buza-**ni** ku-lo

SM.PST.1-say aug-1a.son 1a.AS-1a.Ntabatha ask.IMP-2PL LOC-PRO.11
 ‘Ntabatha's son said, "You ask her."' [BU160401O]

The prefix *yi-*, or sometimes *hi-*, used with monosyllabic stems, is glossed IMP.

77. wafika wathi **hima** apha
 wa-fik-a wa-thi **hi**-ma apha
 SM.PST.1-arrive-FV SM.PST.1-say IMP-stand.IMP here
 ‘He arrived and said “stand here”...’ [BU160401O]

If there is derivational morphology, i.e., something intervening between the root and the final vowel, we segment the final *-a* and gloss it as IMP. Note that the vowel of the imperative prefix *yi-* merges with a vowel-initial stem:

78. *Xelela / yenzela uNopink(i) intsomi*
 Xel-el-**a** **yi**-enz-el-**a** u-Nopinki i-ntsomi
 tell-APPL-IMP IMP-do-APPL-IMP AUG-1a.Nopinki AUG-9.story
 ‘Tell. Narrate a story for Nopinki.’ [MN180626O_b]

7.8 **Auxiliary verbs**

Auxiliaries that have an obvious or established form such as *khe/kha* ‘once’ or *ngekhe* ‘never’, *soko/soloko* ‘always’, are glossed with their translation and POS tagged as VAUX. They are considered lexicalized and are limited in number.

Auxiliaries with more transparent etymology and inflection, are glossed and segmented as regular verbs. They can still be found as they are POS tagged as VAUX.

79. *Umane soko engaphiwa*
 U-**man**-e soko e-nga-ph-iw-a
 SM.1-keep.doing-SBJV always SM1.PRT-NEG-offer-PASS-FV
 ‘He is often not offered’ [BU160401O]

When *ya-* ‘go’ is used as an auxiliary, it can function as an itive, but it can also have other functions. If it is an itive function, we gloss it with *go.IT* in order to make it searchable both as an itive marker and an auxiliary verb ‘go’. It is also tagged as VAUX.

80. *Kuye kwafika abantu*
 Ku-y-e kwa-fik-a a-ba-ntu
 SM.17-go.IT-REC.CJ SM.PST.17-arrive-FV AUG-NCP.2-2.person
 ‘People arrived...’ [BU151210S_a]

7.9 **Negation**

7.9.1 *Negative morpheme -a*

The negative morpheme *a-* is segmented and glossed NEG. When there is a special subject marker for the negative (in noun class 1), this is marked as NEG. Other subject markers are just marked with SM.#, also when negated. A glide is formed between the negative prefix and a subject marker that is only a vowel. This glide is included in the underlying form, as with *yi-* in the main verb in this example:

81. *akazange ayivume*
a-ka-zange **a-yi-vum-e**
 NEG-SM.NEG.1-never NEG-SM.9-agree-REC.CJ
 ‘She really didn’t agree’ [PSJ150517O]

Zange and *khange* can be used on their own, preceding an inflected verb. We translate both as ‘never’. There is a distinction; *zange* being more far past than *khange*, but we don’t reflect this in glossing.

7.9.2 Negative ending *-anga*

The negative ending *-anga* is used in the recent past. It is segmented with the initial *-a* and not just *-nga*. It is glossed NEG.REC. Before the verb root, there can be a negative prefix *nga-* or *nge-* which we gloss NEG:

82. *Ubuya ungedibananga nogqirha*
 u-buy-a u-**nge**-diban-**anga** na-u-gqirha
 SM.2SG-return-FV SM.2SG-NEG-meet-NEG.REC COM-AUG-1a.doctor
 ‘you return without having met the doctor’ [GX150515M_a]

7.9.3 Negative imperative

The negative imperative is often abbreviated from *musaku-* to *suku-*, we do not segment this morpheme. We gloss it as NEG.IMP:

83. *sukumphatha*
suku-m-phath-a
 NEG.IMP-OM.1-touch-FV
 ‘don’t touch him/her.’ [BLN150924M]

7.9.4 Ironic negative

For ironic negatives (Slater 2025) – a negative predicate that is interpreted as (very) positive – the first negative morpheme is glossed NEG.IR:

84. *asibaninzi*
a-si-ba-ninzi
 NEG.IR-SM.1PL-AC.2-many
 ‘we are many’ (lit. ‘we are not many’). [GU151208D_f]

It follows that the whole phrase is ironic negative, without making the glossing too long. The literal negative reading is included in brackets, in the same way as with metaphorical translations (see Section 10.3).

7.10 Conjunctions

Xhosa exhibits a range of conjunctions based on the infinitive *ukuba* ‘to be’. We do not segment *ukuba*. A translation is given, which can be different depending on the context (‘then’, ‘when’). The *ku* is often not heard. In this case, we write what the person says, e.g., *uba* and not *u(ku)ba*. Other conjunctions related to *ukuba* are also not segmented, when they

always appear in the same form, such as *kangakuba* ‘so much so that’. The appropriate translation is given.

I-noku-ba ‘it could be’ [SM.9-POSSIB-be], on the other hand, could change and be for example *u-noku-ba* ‘s/he could be’ [SM.1-POSSIB-be], so here it makes more sense to segment. Also *ingathi* ‘like’ changes in agreement, so we do segment (also in order to reflect the potential modality). *I-nga-thi* SM.9-POT-say.

We don’t write a presumably dropped infinitive prefix, such as for *funeka* ‘must’, which also appears as *kufuneka* with the same meaning.

8. Adverbials

8.1 Adverbs

The most common adverbials like *ekuseni* ‘in the morning time’, are annotated only with their translations, without segmentation. This includes adverbs with *ka-* like: *kamnandi* ‘nicely’. In some cases we have used the Greater Dictionary isiXhosa as a guideline. For example, *ekuseni* ‘in the morning time’ has its own entry in the dictionary, but not *kwilanga*, which is why it is segmented *ku-ilanga* ‘in the day’.

An additional test for categorising a word as adverb is if the word can occur post-verbally or independently (e.g., as an answer: *kakhulu!* ‘a lot!’) – we therefore do not segment it.

8.2 Place adverbials

Place adverbials are POS-tagged as adverbials. They are glossed with their translation, unless they form part of the demonstrative paradigm, such as *pha/phaya* ‘here’. In that case we gloss them in the same way as demonstratives (see Section 3.5).

85. *bahlala phaya*
ba-hlal-a **phaya**
SM.2-stay-FV DEM.DIST.16
'they stay there' [MN180626O_b]

The adverbial *khona* is glossed with the translation ‘there’.

8.3 Adverbials with -nye

The adverbial *kunye* ‘together’ is invariable and therefore not segmented. Unlike *kwenye* and *komnye*. The latter two are segmented whereas *kunye* is not segmented and just glossed with the translation ‘together’:

86. *kwenye*
ku-e-nye
LOC-AC.9-another
'at another' [BLN150924M]
87. *komnye umzi*
ku-o-m-nye u-m-zi
LOC-AUG-AC.3-another AUG-NCP.3-3.house
'at another house' [MN180626O_a]

88. *kunye*
 kunye
 together
 ‘together’ [BU151210S_b]

9. Parts of speech

The words in the corpus are also tagged for their parts of speech (POS).

We POS-tag items with adjectival functions as ADJ, i.e., adjectives and nominal relatives. We tag all numerals and countwords as NUM (numeral), even ‘first’ which is the relative form of the verb *-qala* ‘begin’.
 All relative verbs are POS-tagged V.

9.1 Derived nouns

Words that are used as nouns but derived from verbs, are PoS tagged as nouns.

10. Transcription conventions

10.1 Elided vowels

Curly brackets in Korp { } indicate that the vowel is not heard. In this document they have been changed to ordinary brackets ():

89. *sitye isidlo sasek(u)seni*
 si-ty-e i-si-dlo sa-se-ku**seni**
 sm.1pl-eat-sbjv aug-ncp.7-food AS.7-LOC.COP-morning
 ‘We will eat breakfast.’ [BU160331M_a]

We have opted to only indicate when a vowel is elided, such as the final vowel. When the transcriber feels that an entire morpheme is elided, this morpheme is not included in the transcription. For example, a person might say *ndizovuka*, but the transcriber thinks it should be *ndizokuvuka*. In order not to be prescriptive and alter what is actually said, we eventually decided to not transcribe *ndizo(ku)vuka* in such cases, but to stick with *ndizovuka*. Instances of leaving the morpheme in might still be present in the corpus.

When a morpheme ending in a vowel is followed by a vowel initial morpheme, the vowels coalesce. We indicate the underlying forms in the segmentation row, such as with *nendoda* in the following example:

90. *kwathi badibana nendoda*
 kwa-thi ba-dib-an-a na-i-ndoda
 SM.PST.17-say SM.PST.2-meet-RECP-FV COM-AUG-9.man
 ‘They met a man..’ [BU160401O]

We also indicate the underlying form when the vowels that coalesce are the same, such as with the comitative *na-* followed by *abantu* ‘people’ in example (91):

rule of thumb. When a word has Xhosa inflection, it is tagged as its word class, for example N (noun) or V (verb).

10.5 *Overlap*

When speakers overlap, we indicate this with square brackets, in the speech of both speakers who are overlapping:

95. [owokuqala]
 o-wa-uku-qala
 RV.SM.2SG-AS.1-INF-first
 ‘the first one’
 [owesibini]
 o-wa-i-si-bini
 RV.SM.2SG-AS.1-AUG-NCP.7-7.two
 ‘the second one’ [BU151209D_b]

10.6 *Abbreviations in Xhosa*

Abbreviations in Xhosa are left as abbreviations, e.g. SPS (‘Senior Primary School’):

96. *Utish(a) eGcinisizwe SPS* <low_voice>
 U-tish-a e-Gcinisizwe SPS
 SM.1-teach-FV LOC-gcinisizwe SPS
 ‘She teaches at Gcinisizwe SPS.’ [BLN150925M_b]

10.7 *Vowel coalescence with particles*

Vowel coalescence also occurs when particles are added to other words, such as with the particle *njenga* ‘like’ in (97). We make use of the equals sign in the segmentation row, following the Leipzig Glossing Rules:

97. *simoje / njengkubraya*
 si-m-oj-e njenga=uku-braya
 SM.1PL-OM.1-roast-SBJV like=INF-barbeque
 ‘and roast as when you braai..’ [GX150515M_c]

Acknowledgements

We are thankful for advise about glossings from the following people: Stefan Savic, Jochen Zeller, Bastian Persohn, Jenneke van der Wal and Thera Crane.

This research has been made possible through the generous funding of the Swedish Research Council under three consequent projects: ‘Morphosyntactic variation in the dialects of Xhosa’, ‘The role of the verb phrase and word order in the expression of definiteness in Bantu languages’, and ‘How do words get in order? The role of speaker-hearer interaction in languages of southern Africa’.

The support of the University of Gothenburg, including Språkbanken Text, as well as Rhodes University, is thankfully acknowledged.

References

- Bloom Ström, Eva-Marie. 2018. Linguistic and sociolinguistic aspects of variation in the Eastern Cape: complexities of Xhosa language use. *Studia Orientalia Electronica* 6:90-120.
- Bloom Ström, Eva-Marie, Onelisa Slater, Aron Zahran, Aleksandrs Berdicevskis and Anne Schumacher. 2023. Preparing a corpus of spoken Xhosa. In Ellen Breitholtz, Shalom Lappin, Sharid Loaiciga, Nikolai Ilinykh and Simon Dobnik (eds): *Proceedings of the 2023 CLASP Conference on Learning with Small Data (LSD)*, 62-67. Gothenburg: Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Comrie, Bernard, Martin Haspelmath and Balthasar Bickel. 2008, updated 2015. *The Leipzig Glossing Rules: Conventions for interlinear morpheme-by-morpheme glosses* (ed.) Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology. Leipzig.
- Kirsch, Beverley and Silvia Skorge. 2010. *Complete Xhosa*. London: McGraw-Hill.
- Mini, B.M, S. L. Tshabe, F.M. Shoba and P.N. van der Westhuizen. 2003. *The greater dictionary of isiXhosa, volume 2 K-P*. Alice: IsiXhosa National Lexicography Unit.
- Oosthuysen, Jacobus C. 2016. *The grammar of isiXhosa*. Stellenbosch: SUN MeDIA.
- Slater, Onelisa. 2025. *Ironic negatives in isiXhosa*. MA thesis. Makhanda: Rhodes University.